

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AS A PROCESS OF LEARNING PHYSICAL CULTURE
AND IMPLEMENTATION IN HEALTH EDUCATION

WYCHOWANIE FIZYCZNE JAKO PROCES UCZENIA SIĘ KULTURY FIZYCZNEJ
A REALIZACJA W EDUKACJI ZDROWOTNEJ

ФІЗИЧНЕ ВИХОВАННЯ ЯК ПРОЦЕС НАВЧАННЯ ФІЗИЧНІЙ КУЛЬТУРИ
ТА ІМПЛЕМЕНТАЦІЇ В ОЗДОРОВЧУ ОСВІТУ

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Анотації

This article will address the topic of physical education and health education as processes of learning physical culture, especially through the prism of teaching methodology in schools. The broadly understood physical culture requires that students and the whole society be made aware that it is not only a sport, but also everything that is with it, and given the inseparable connection between sport and health, one can not overlook the important role of education in this area.

Key words: sport, physical culture, health education, learning.

W niniejszym artykule poruszony zostanie wątek wychowania fizycznego i edukacji zdrowotnej jako procesów uczenia się kultury fizycznej, zwłaszcza przez pryzmat metodyki nauczania w szkołach. Szeroko rozumiana kultura fizyczna wymaga uświadomienia uczniom i całemu społeczeństwu, że jest to nie tylko sport, ale również wszystko to, co się z nim wiąże, a biorąc pod uwagę nierozzerwalny związek sportu i zdrowia nie można pominąć istotnej roli edukacji w tym zakresie.

Słowa kluczowe: sport, kultura fizyczna, edukacja zdrowotna, uczenie się.

У цій статті розглянуто тему фізичного виховання та оздоровчого виховання як процесів навчання фізичної культури, особливо через призму методики викладання у школах. Широко зрозуміла фізична культура вимагає дати учням та всьому суспільству усвідомлення того, що це не лише спорт, а й все, що з ним пов'язано, та враховуючи нерозривний взаємозв'язок між спортом та здоров'ям, важливу роль освіти в цій галузі не можна ігнорувати.

Ключові слова: спорт, фізична культура, оздоровче виховання, навчання.

Admission. The basis of modern physical culture is sport, tourism, various forms of games and motion games. They are the resources of traffic forms, from which specialists shape patterns of physical, psychological and social activity [1].

Physical culture is a work on itself that is the essence of self-education and self-present, including activities with attention to health, construction and posture of the body, physical development of the human being and shaping, improving his or her physical abilities, fitness and physical efficiency as well as individual and social behavior and needs. Physical education is a conscious activity focused on the creation of the right set of attitudes and attitudes related with the passing of messages, as well as harden-

ing on the stimuli of the environment and acquiring skills and skills that determine the behavior of a person in relation to his physical fitness. Physical education has a purpose to shape a child in the right direction of development as well as health. Health is the first, but not the only, goal of physical education. The pedagogues pass on to the young generation the achievements of physical culture, implementing them to use various forms of this culture and to participate in situations of fair entertainment, rest and self-improvement.

Generally raising means the process of preparing the young generation for an adult, independent life. This process includes the overall impact on the juvenile, which are aimed at the development of various dispositions of the child, because the child is living an important development path from childhood to the onset

of adolescence. Depending on what physical level and psychological will be achieved, from the acquired knowledge and skills, from awareness, activity, and social creation and moral will depend on its success in the next years of learning and success not only at school, but also in life. The condition for effective conduct is mainly knowledge and skills, while attitude and motivation is a prerequisite for socially desirable behavior.

Methodology of physical education

The task of the methodology of physical education is to create a rational, structural model of realizing theory in practice. Physical education is not only a subject of teaching with a specific dimension of program hours. It is also that the whole of interaction in didactic-educational work at school, related with physical development and physical fitness of the child, as well as an integral part of upbringing. The conduct of physical education classes and its methodology differ radically from other teaching subjects, since the contents of the lesson and their organization have a different specificity [2].

Physical education includes a set of measures whose most general feature is the movement, exercise and development of the child's personality. These funds can be divided into several groups mutually complementary. Are it's fun and movement games, gymnastics with elements of upbringing Musical-movement, exercises and training games, trips and sports: athletics, team sports games, swimming, winter sports. Transfer of knowledge and skills are made by influencing the intellectual and fitness realm. Shaping attitudes and motivations occurs as a result of influencing the emotional-volitional sphere.

The impact on both spheres consists of a process called education in a broad sense or education. In practical operation, learning processes cannot be separated and upbringing, which does not mean that the effects are always consistent. Therefore, according to the statement of H. Muszyński, who said that: "... there is no automatic relationship between the shaping of knowledge and human skills and shaping his attitudes and ideals". It follows that there is no clear relationship between teaching and upbringing [3].

Physical education in general terms can be presented as a bi-directional relationship be-

tween a physical educator and a foster child. Developing the conclusions of H. Grabowski from 1987, the stages of development of views on the essence of physical education can be shown in the following way: education (body shaping), education through the body, shaping the body and upbringing, upbringing in caring for the body (education in physical culture). The first three concepts reflect the traditional look of what physical education is, while the latter concept comes from the contemporary pedagogically oriented theory of physical education. In this concept, upbringing for the sake of the body gradually began to transfer the specific features of physical education from the exclusively and purely instrumental zone to the sphere of proper education, that is, the intended formation of a new set of attitudes, beliefs and values. Therefore, physical education should be understood as a process that creates the right set of attitudes and attitudes that determine human behavior in relation to its physical form.

According to Osiński, physical education is an intentional and conscious activity, aimed at creating the right set of attitudes and attitudes, communicating basic messages, as well as implementation for hardening to environmental stimuli and gaining motor skills, improving the efficiency and posture of the body. These categories determine the behavior of a man in relation to his physical form. Physical education is understood as a constant work on one's own corporality in all periods of individual life. It fulfills the role of stimulation, adaptation and correction factors. When referring to physical education, it must be said that physical education should play the same role for students. The stimulus function for pupils should cover the totality of their behaviors, views and actions. Pupil from the beginning to be excited and know how to proceed, in your life to acquire knowledge, skills, abilities and the right attitude.

Often it is to be stimulated to make him want to learn about physical education and everything related to him. The student must, therefore, be treated as a subject of influence that interacts with a physical education teacher. The teacher must see to it that the student could in an appropriate and reasonable shape your personality. The function preparing for conscious care for the body, after the end of the educational relationship, is the second task. The student must be

so directed and prepared that after finishing school he does not finish physical education, so he would continue to care for beauty, health, physical condition, taking active part in various forms of physical activity.

Physical education as a process of education and upbringing

The very word process (Latin: processus – conduct) means the course of the following phenomena that are interrelated in a given causal relationship. The process can also be defined as a sequence of events related to one essential goal. The widest concept here is the educational environment, which includes from the point of view of the educational goal, both intentional and unintentional influences. This climate is like a background for all education processes. A narrower concept is education, which includes intentional and deliberately targeted changes in the human personality. However, this part of education, which is primarily aimed at causing positive changes in the individual's consciousness and creating a proper set of attitudes in relation to its physical form, we call physical education. In this sense, each process of education and physical education is the basic unit of physical education with a specific physical structure. Every process of upbringing and physical education is always in the first place a conscious and intentional interference leading to changes in this sphere of personality of the individual, which concerns his relation to his physical form.

These actions can be described as education in the narrower sense of the word. There are also relations connected with systematically undertaken activities enabling the pupils to master specific knowledge – intellectualization, as well as with the production of certain skills and fitness. These processes can be described as learning - teaching. There are also activities that directly and directly relate to the relationship (forces of nature – the body) and which it is difficult to attribute the full features of "education" or "learning - teaching".

We are thinking here about activities undertaken to teach motor activities, immediate improvement of physical fitness, motor skills, body posture or resistance to environmental stimuli. We define these processes as learning and teaching as education. Therefore, we will

understand the processes of upbringing and physical education as a certain orderly sequence of educational and educational activities systematically undertaken by educators, and enabling the induction of certain desired changes in the sphere of beliefs and attitudes, knowledge, skills, motor skills, efficiency, resilience of the system and construction and postures of the body that determine the behavior of the juvenile, and the relationship to his physical form. The socio-cultural place in the modern world that are reflected in the state of physical health, mental and the social human population. Both theoreticians and practitioners dealing with health issues agree that modern knowledge allows to indicate the causes of many diseases, stressing the thesis that maintaining good health is the resultant of many significant factors. Studies that indicate that human health are widely known to the highest degree depends on his lifestyle, which manifests itself in sets of behaviors, habits and health habits. Lifestyle as a determinant of health, an important indicator of the level of health culture, physical culture and the individual and society [4].

School as an environment of education for physical culture

The subject of our interests is young people in the period of psychophysical development and its social conditions related to physical activity. Mental, physical and social health is the goal and conditions for multilateral development in all forms and levels of sporting activities in the case of two sides – teacher and student, sportsman and trainer. In sport, no matter what we grow, health is the most important factor. Education for health is the basic right of every child. Health is an inseparable condition for school achievements, for the quality of life and for economic effects. By providing children with knowledge about health, shaping their attitudes, skills and habits, we can help them healthy lifestyle and work, and thus improve the health of the public. Child to could well learn, be healthy sit m.

The school in the field of physical education is the most important source. It is in a primary school physical education classes should be made using the process of physical culture so that children and young people preparing for adult life. The child achieves physical fitness

through physical games and physical exercises and sport that shape a man not only physically but also mentally, socially and morally. This physical education teacher has the most important contribution to shaping the interest in the physical activity of children and youth, he has in this respect, the greatest opportunities, especially in the process of lesson and extracurricular activities, where it takes into account the personal and developmental diversity of children. Finding such a system of motivation to engage them during physical education classes, it becomes become the main problem of work. It is increasingly difficult to mobilize children and young people to participate in class and extracurricular activities. Many teachers are increasingly the most attention is paid to how to mobilize and motivate students to actively participate in the classes. They use various measures and methods to stimulate students to attend school activities. A teacher of physical education can meet in school practice It is necessary to develop students' specific types or features of attention that are important for the effective implementation of sports tasks.

This is needed in the teaching process and upbringing. It is important when working with children that the teaching process activates the involuntary attention of the pupils. For this reason, classes should bring new elements that trigger curiosity and interest among pupils, as the constant repetition of what has already happened, can cause fatigue, distraction and discouragement among the students. That's why it's also a teacher in the classroom should look for ways to strengthen the involuntary attention in the emotional sphere of an athlete by arousing his interests. Many factors influence the course of motivation to physical activity in the school; however the teacher has the biggest influence on the pupils' participation. Activities that are interestingly prepared, running in a relaxed atmosphere, arouse students' satisfaction. The child slowly begins to turn d of exercise, it is born in the ear on the need in the future and develops a passion for physical activity. Skillful adjustment of the form of effort to the psychophysical abilities of children stimulates in them involuntary attention and ease of concentration on exercises.

Physical education classes should implement a system of grading the problem, so that partici-

pants will feel the pleasure associated with exercise. When preparing and organizing classes, the teacher should offer the student the most diversity of experiences in terms of the content taught, the forms and means used. The organized classes may be motivating in the natural environment, through the organization of various games and motion games, which can be not only useful, but very interesting. It can be a basic and also the most desirable incentive factor for interested children. If there is interest in the motive, a lasting and desired educational effect can be created. They will not be possible if you use anxiety or ambition motives, where you can block the activity of children. That is why the course of classes consisting in motivating pupils' activity is so important. Physical and health activity has a significant impact and importance for the proper functioning of the human body in the physical sphere and psychic. It is also important that in free time there is a significant need to supplement the effort. That is why health and sports education already taken up plays an important role in early childhood education. The need for physical activity should be aroused in children from an early age. Physical education teacher should to develop in students the passion for physical activity by shaping appropriate habits and skills, which are the basic goals of didactic work and upbringing from the elementary school. The development of children's passion for children will consist of pleasant experiences, resulting not only of interestingly carried out forms of exercise, but also organization of activities in which I will not be eager for monotony. Developing this kind of passion is not an easy task, sometimes even minor unpleasant situations or incidents can disrupt or completely destroy this process. That is why the atmosphere and the creation of conditions in which the child can count on the support and help from the teacher will be important.

Health education at school

Requirements, skills, scope of the subject of physical education, including health education at particular stages of education, are defined in the core curriculum. The commentary on the website of the Ministry of National Education in December 27 December 2013 precisely formulates the tasks of the school and teachers related to this subject. "A new solution in the education

system is the link between health education and physical education:

- at the first stage of education, the area of "physical education and health education" was distinguished,

- at the second, third and fourth education stage, it was recorded that physical education "plays a leading role in health education",

- in junior high schools and upper secondary schools, the thematic block "health education" was separated,

- the scope of health education was expanded to include aspects of psychosocial health, with particular emphasis on life skills (personal and social). The basis for constructing the "health education" block in physical education was the adoption of the definition and objectives of this education:

- o health education is a didactic and educational process in which students learn how to live, to: preserve and improve their own health and other people and create a healthy environment, and in the case of illness or disability actively participate in its treatment, cope and reduce its negative effects,

- o about the goal of health education for children and adolescents is to help them in:

- getting to know each other, tracking the progress of their development, identifying and solving health problems,

- understanding what health is, what determines why and how to care for it,

- developing a sense of responsibility for your own health and for other people's health,

- strengthening your self-esteem and belief in your abilities,

- developing personal and social skills conducive to well-being and positive adaptation to the tasks and challenges of everyday life,

- preparation for participation in health activities and creating a healthy environment at home, school, work place, local community (health education is an important element of civic education).

Content in the field of health education has been in addition to physical education included in many subjects, m. al.: early childhood education, biology, education for family life, knowledge about society, education for safety, entrepreneurship, religion and ethics. Health education contents contain the answer on current trends in the behavior of children and

young people, and these in turn are reflected in the tests carried out" [5].

In addition to physical activity, the Ministry of Health Education emphasizes the importance of healthy nutrition of pupils for their proper physical and mental development. In order to carry out these tasks, it is necessary for schools to undertake all types of activities in the area of supporting a healthy lifestyle of students. These activities are defined in school educational programs and prevention. They cover all areas of school life. The more attractive and interesting tasks, the greater the motivation of students to implement them. School in the field of health education tasks, they carry out various programs, e.g.

- Hold the form,
- Live tasty and healthy,
- Breakfast gives you power,
- Healthy breakfast day,
- 5 servings of fruits and vegetables,
- Do not burn with me, please,
- Clean air around us,
- Find the right solution,
- Prevention of cervical cancer – Human papilloma infection,
- Log out to life,
- Time for health,
- MultiSport,
- Junior Sport,
- Little Master,
- Universal swimming lessons,
- Fruit at school,
- A glass of milk.

Great motivation encouraging and preparing young people for healthy and active lifestyle is nationwide the "Health Promoting Schools" program. Schools implementing this program, plan your work and take action based on five standards of health promoting school:

1. They help members of the school community (including parents) to understand and accept the concept of a school promoting health.

2. They manage health promotion projects in a way that promotes:

- participation, partnership and cooperation of the school community (incl parents) and the local community,
- effectiveness and long-term activities.

3. They conduct health education of students and employees and strive to increase its quality and effectiveness.

4. They create a favorable social climate:

- satisfaction from learning and working at school, achieving successes and strengthening the self-esteem of students and employees,
- health and development of students and employees,
- participation, partnership and cooperation of members of the school community, parents and people from the local community [6].

Creating a friendly work environment, education and upbringing is especially important for all members of the school community – including parents, teachers and directors. There is an important task ahead of them: in their daily work they are to disseminate a healthy and active lifestyle and promote proper habits of taking care of their health. Care for health it is a process of discovering, using, protecting and developing the potential of our body, mind, environment, our spirituality, family and community. It is also important to excite in children, the need for physical activity.

Important features in the methodology of modern health education of children and adolescents include:

- focus on the learning process,
- the role of the teacher as a guide, adviser to students (not an expert),
- teacher modeling of desirable attitudes and health behaviors,
- asking students about their needs and encouraging them to participate in the planning of the curriculum,
- using activation methods,
- using the learning through experience cycle,
- creating an atmosphere conducive to building trust, motivation and activity during classes.

End. Considering all information related to physical education of children and young people, it can be said that it is an important element of education. He devotes a lot of attention to this problem, recognizing that this is one of the basic pillars of raising a young man. Physical health goes hand in hand with proper mental development, and this gives a chance for a happy adult life.

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